

Liquid intrusion and evaporation in low-pressure cavities: numerical investigation with STAR-CCM+

Einströmung und Verdampfung einer Flüssigkeit unter Niederdruckbedingungen: numerische Simulationen mit STAR-CCM+

Masterarbeit

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1 Introduction

Their potential to host extraterrestrial life has made icy moons, such as the Jovian moon Europa and Saturn's moon Enceladus, prime targets for exploration in the upcoming decades. The Cassini-Huygens mission discovered active cryovolcanism on Enceladus in 2005 in the form of water rich plumes erupting from the south polar region (Fig. 1b). These plumes consist mainly of water vapour, ice particles along with dissolved gases with a source rate estimated to be 300 kg/s and supply most of the material making up Saturn's E ring.[1, 2]

The mechanisms of cryovolcanism and the disparity between the recorded flow behaviour and constituents of the plumes are subject to ongoing research. Various models aim to explain the plume mechanics and the observed flow behaviour - explosive boiling due to exposure of the subsurface ocean to vacuum due to cracks opened by tidal stresses; simulating the fissures in the surface as convergent-divergent (de Laval) nozzles that accelerate the vapor to the observed supersonic speeds; or channels inside the icy crust acting as a de Laval nozzle where the grains are initially decelerated due to frequent wall collisions before being re-accelerated by the vapour flow. [2, 3] To be able to use plumes as a surrogate to learn about the subsurface ocean, a better understanding of their driving processes is key.

Figure 1: Enceladus and its cryovolcanic plumes. Credit: NASA/JPL/Space Science Institute.

(a) Distant view of Enceladus.

(b) Enhanced, colour-coded image of the plumes outlining their extreme extents.

In an effort to contribute to the understanding of the fluid dynamics of the supersonic plumes, an experimental setup is under development at FH Aachen - University of Applied Sciences. In collaboration with the Rocket Experiments for University Students (REXUS) programme of the German Aerospace Center (DLR) and the Swedish

Space Agency (SNSA), the experimental setup will be installed on a sounding rocket and will perform under reduced gravity and vacuum conditions. The experiment consists of heated liquid water being let into a chamber connected to a de Laval nozzle, initially filled with low-pressure air. The nozzle lid is opened after a short time period and this depressurisation of the chamber is expected to result in vaporisation of the water present in the evaporation chamber.

1.1 Experimental Setup

The 'flow system assembly' in the experimental setup, as shown in Fig. 2, consists of the hydraulic accumulator, the evaporation chamber, and the injection system subassembly that drives the liquid from the hydraulic accumulator into the evaporation chamber. In the current design of the setup, these components are assembled vertically and the water is driven up into the evaporation chamber. The evaporation chamber is constructed out of aluminium and can be assumed to be separated into a water reservoir and the nozzle.

The hydraulic accumulator and the evaporation chamber can be heated until lift-off. Current design considerations assume the temperature of the evaporation chamber and water in the accumulator to be 368.15 K and 353.15 K respectively. The ambient temperature at lift-off is assumed to be 280 K based on the remarks and considerations made during reviews of one such previous FH Aachen experiment. The flow system assembly is sealed off before lift-off and an initial pressure of 1 bar is assumed in the evaporation chamber, initially occupied by air. The hydraulic accumulator is sufficiently insulated and the nozzle is encased in a golden foil to minimise the amount of heat lost. No stipulations have been made regarding the evaporation chamber, however as there is no fluid convection during operation, losses are assumed to be minimum.

Water injection begins after the electronics module signals the start of data storage and ends shortly before the apogee is reached. Due to water remaining at the time of cutoff in the injection subassembly and also the accumulator, the total amount of water discharged to the chamber is assumed to be 150 mL. A constant mass flow rate

Figure 2: Schematic of the flow system assembly.

of 15 mL/s is assumed. The inflow velocity in the actual experiment can be tuned to desired values. Discharge time in the simulation is calculated based on the estimated water level at the end of discharge. A minimum time of 6 s and a system pressure of 1.7 bar is assumed before the electronics system signals the opening of the nozzle lid ensuing the vaporisation of the water. As no active heating is provided, the phase change also takes place in the fluid bulk. This process is facilitated by the presence of nucleation points that are found in the water as 2.5 g of silicates per 100 mL of water. The silicates are assumed to be spherical with a uniform diameter of $0.8 \mu\text{m}$. At the start of depressurisation, these 'seed' points are assumed to be uniformly distributed in the water bulk.

1.2 Multiphase Flows and Star-CCM+

Multiphase flows are characterised by the simultaneous flow of several phases. Regardless of our improved understanding of such flows, multiphase flows remain complicated to model. Multiphase flows are multiscale in nature - where the cascading effects of various physics acting over system-level to the microscopic scale must be taken into account [4]. Along with turbulence, multiple deformable, moving interfaces pose discontinuities in the fluid properties and induce fluctuations in the flow variables in the neighbourhood. The distribution of the phases cannot be accurately estimated a priori [5] but the macroscopic behaviour of the system is dependent on small-scale interactions of the phases [6]. These evolving interfacial structures tend to directly affect the inertial and thermodynamical development of the flow field. [4]

Two-phase liquid-gas flows can be classified into three main flow regimes based on the distribution of the phases - dispersed flow, transitional flow, and separated flow. This ranges from bubbly flows - where small gas bubbles are finely dispersed through the continuous liquid phase, to the separated flows - where a sharp interface marks the boundary between the two phases. The transitional flow regime is marked by the presence of both dispersed and separated flows. [5]

Star-CCM+ is a commercial CFD software currently maintained and developed by Siemens Digital Industries Software. The software uses the Finite Volume Method to discretise the integral form of the governing differential equations over a number of control volumes in the domain. The software has an automatic meshing system but allows the implementation of custom meshing using surface wrappers. [7]

1.3 Objectives and Outline

As the two main physical processes in the experiment - liquid infiltration and subsequent evaporation - take place in very distinct flow regimes and at separated points in time, we divide the experiment into two subproblems -

- the infiltration of heated water in the evaporation chamber exposed to ambient temperature conditions,
- and the evaporation of superheated water in the evaporation subject to depressurisation.

We will refer to the infiltration subdivision as the infiltration subproblem, and the flash evaporation as the evaporation/flash evaporation subproblem. This thesis will investigate the modelling of the two processes in the commercial CFD software tool - STAR-CCM+. We investigate the theoretical framework of modelling the experiment under the constraints of our general understanding of the physics behind rapid non-equilibrium phase change and the capabilities of a general purpose CFD solver. We study flash evaporation from a thermodynamics and kinetic theory viewpoint and identify the primary contributing factors important for the accurate capture of the flow phenomenon. Due to the complex and multiscale nature of the phenomenon, a working simulation could not be modelled. A theoretical framework is described and possible ways of implementation are discussed.

The theoretical framework behind separated flows as in the infiltration problem is also discussed. The infiltration process is modelled using the Volume-of-Fluid method based on the one-fluid formulation of two-phase flows. We investigate the flow behaviour and assess the conditions in the system that would be expected at the start of the depressurisation process.

The thesis is divided into four parts. Section 2 introduces the most important concepts and reviews the theory behind flash evaporation. We review the existing practices in modelling evaporation, boiling, and flash evaporation to different degrees of complexity. Phase stability of superheated liquids, nucleation based on classical nucleation theory, and bubble growth in superheated liquids as a free-moving boundary problem involving phase change is studied. Free surface flows without phase change are a simplification of this problem. Two multiphase models are identified relevant to the two subproblems - the one-fluid and two-fluid formulation respectively. Turbulence modelling is briefly discussed in the context of multiphase flows.

Section 3 discusses the numerical implementation of the two mathematical models in the context of STAR-CCM+. Closure relations for the interphase momentum and heat transfer are reviewed and an attempt is made to identify the most general closures. We discuss the implementation of adaptive mesh refinement based on user defined criteria for 2D domains in STAR-CCM+. The mathematical model of the two subproblems is laid out - assumptions involved in the modelling considerations are defined along with the governing equations and jump conditions.

The numerical results are described in Section 4. In order to benchmark STAR-CCM+'s modelling of two-phase flows in the presence of free-moving boundaries, the 1D Stefan problem and the 2D Rayleigh-Taylor instability are modelled. Numerical results are

compared with the analytical solutions in case of the Stefan problem and existing DNS studies for the Rayleigh-Taylor instability. The simulation setup for the infiltration problem is described. A grid convergence study is undertaken to investigate the spatial and temporal dependence of the solution on the mesh and timestep size. We finally comment on the evolution of the flow behaviour during infiltration and estimate the initial conditions for the second subproblem.

All findings are summarised in Section 5 along with suggestions for improvements and future work.

2 Modelling the Physical Problem

This chapter describes the evaporation of superheated fluids. The physical and mathematical foundation for flash evaporation of superheated liquids under low-pressure and reduced-gravity conditions are discussed. It reviews metastability and superheat limits, nucleation pathways, and bubble-growth regimes, connecting these to kinetic interfacial mass transfer. It then surveys model classes and delineates when non-equilibrium and slip must be resolved, before formulating one-fluid and two-fluid macroscopic balances, interfacial jump conditions, and RANS turbulence modeling choices pertinent to separated and dispersed regimes.

2.1 Evaporation

Evaporation processes are characterised based on whether they occur at saturation temperatures or not. Evaporation at saturation temperatures, known as vaporisation, is a much faster process in comparison to evaporation at normal temperatures. Here, the metastability of liquids becomes relevant and the inception of vaporisation is governed by how far a liquid can enter the metastable zone.

(a) Phase diagram of water showing initial and final experimental state regions relevant to flash evaporation. (b) Spinodal lines and metastable regions for a liquid on a P-v diagram.

Figure 3: Thermodynamic stability of water

A liquid that is heated above its equilibrium saturation temperature without undergoing phase change is termed as being metastable and exists in a non-equilibrium condition. The degree of superheat is

$$\Delta T = T - T_{\text{sat}}, \tag{2.1}$$

where T is the temperature of the bulk liquid and T_{sat} is the saturation temperature at the system pressure. In instances of depressurisation, the difference between the minimum pressure after depressurisation and the saturation pressure corresponding to the initial temperature is called the pressure undershoot. The metastable states can be assumed to lie along an isotherm extending from the stable single-phase liquid region into the vapour dome, eventually reaching the metastable vapour region and then stable vapour phase, as illustrated in Fig. 3. Attainable states throughout this process can be described using a general curve such as BCDE in Fig. 3, where intensity and behaviour of the phase change is strongly dependent on the level of superheat and the pressure undershoot. [8, 9, 10]

Flash evaporation is triggered when the superheat limit of the liquid is reached. The limit of superheat can be the thermodynamic or the kinetic limit based on thermodynamical and kinetic theory considerations respectively. The absolute thermodynamical limit, also known as the spinodal limit, is never practically attained. Vaporisation is always triggered much before the spinodal limit due to internal impurities, density fluctuations, wall nucleation, or the presence of pre-existing nuclei. [9, 10, 11]

In cases where vaporisation occurs along a heated wall, most CFD models distribute the energy transfer by separating the wall heat flux into two components: latent heat absorption associated with bubble vaporisation and sensible heat transferred to the liquid through conduction, convection, and quenching processes. The partitioning depends on the area fractions covered by liquid and vapour phases. Empirical results or models of subprocesses have established correlations between the heat flux and wall superheat. [12, 13]

2.1.1 Vaporisation: Phenomenological and Literature Review

Boiling processes take place due to consistent heat transfer to the system and takes place on the heated surface. Additionally, boiling of pure liquids is an isothermal process that is driven by the difference between the hot surface and the liquid. Flash evaporation is the intense vaporisation triggered by depressurisation of superheated fluids below the saturation pressure. This process induces a violent and transient heat and mass transfer, resulting in the explosive formation and growth of vapour bubbles throughout the liquid volume. The phenomenon is significant in desalination on ships, nuclear reactor safety, and venting of cryogenic propellant tanks, and the harvesting of low-temperature geothermal energy. [14, 15, 16, 17, 18]

Early experiments that systematically studied flash evaporation in liquid pools and sprays in superheated water jets and early empirical correlations to determine the amount of generated vapour were established [19, 20, 21, 22]. For flash evaporation in static pools, the amount of liquid height increased the duration of the phenomenon and the rate of depressurisation increases the intensity. While greater thermal inertia at

larger depths slows the flashing process, the amount of total mass evaporated does not increase proportionally. The total flashed mass scales with superheat via the available sensible-to-latent conversion. [23, 14]

As the flash evaporation process is far from equilibrium, a limiting factor to the vapour generation rate is also the rate at which molecules cross the liquid-vapour interface rather than the rate of bulk heat supply. It has been observed during flashing, that a liquid-vapour interface is generated on the free surface which then progresses into the superheated liquid [24, 25, 26]. High-speed imaging and temperature measurements consistently show that flash evaporation proceeds through three distinct stages: bubble generation, boiling growth, and a boiling reduction stage [15].

Parameters like the non-equilibrium fraction (NEF) and non-equilibrium temperature difference (NETD) have been proposed to quantify the flash evaporation phenomenon. Correlations between the evaporated mass and the dependency on temperature have been obtained by fitting curves to experimental data under various operating conditions. However, the experimental study of the physics remains a challenge due to the inadequacy of measurement techniques that can measure local flow phenomenon accurately. Numerical simulations generally also use the empirical assumptions and relations from specific experiments, making the extension to a general case difficult. [27]

Given the complex nature of flash evaporation, several modelling approaches have been developed to capture different levels of physical fidelity and computational complexity. These approaches vary mainly based on how they treat phase change kinetics and interphase interactions, as summarised in Fig. 4.

Interaction modelling between the phases can be distinguished based on the assumptions of thermal non-equilibrium or relative (slip) velocity between the phases. The incorporation of these assumptions results in an increasingly complex formulation for flashing flow. The resulting four distinct modelling approaches as summarised as follows. [11, 16, 28, 29].

- **Homogeneous Equilibrium Models (HEM)** assume thermal equilibrium and no slip velocity between the phases. Similar to the one-fluid formulation described in Section 2.3.1 where the thermodynamic properties are interpolated from tables or constitutive relations. Sometimes applicable for flows in long pipes where the phases have enough time to achieve equilibrium, HEM tends to underpredict flow rates and is incapable of predicting early time non-equilibrium thermal effects and later time momentum non-equilibrium effects between the phases.
- **Non-Homogeneous Equilibrium Models (NHEM)** treat the system as a mixture but account for slip velocities. With gas volume fractions over 0.3, the relative motion between the phases become significant. The relation of mass-flow rate with changing slip ratios is analysed and the slip ratio that maximises the mass flow rate is assumed. Such correlations for the interphase relative motion tend

Figure 4: Classification of flash evaporation models based on complexity of phase-change modeling and interphase interaction assumptions.

to over-predict the flow rates in comparison to the two-fluid model that assumes thermal and velocity non-equilibrium.

- Homogeneous Non-Equilibrium Models (HNEM)** assume thermal non-equilibrium but do not account for the relative motion between the liquid and vapour phases. While assuming thermal equilibrium underpredicts vapour generation in short geometries, limited understanding of the non-equilibrium physical phenomena such as nucleation and interphase transfers can lead to equally unphysical results while accounting non-equilibrium. HNEMs are primarily boiling delay models based on physical or empirical observations and relaxation models. The boiling models try to emulate the nucleation process as a quasi-step function or trigger flashing inception at a certain superheat threshold. Mixture models need accurate modelling of the vapour generation, interphase momentum transfer, and nucleation rate. Relaxation models solve a rate equation along with a homoge-

neous equilibrium model - the rate equation, based on empirical relaxation times, 'relaxes' the non-equilibrium mixture to the equilibrium state.

- **Non-Homogeneous Non-Equilibrium Models (NHNEM)** such as the drift-flux and two-fluid models are the most general formulations. Although the drift-flux model can be used to model the slip between phases based on other flow field variables, it can't accurately capture non-equilibrium effects. The two-fluid model provides the most general formulation to model flash evaporation, however all interactions and non-equilibrium exchanges must be accurately modelled. The drift-flux model provides a good compromise between the modelling complexity and computational efficiency between the HNEM and the two-fluid formulations.

Modelling phase change becomes similarly convoluted through the incorporation of non-equilibrium and interphase exchanges. While empirical correlations provide a reference estimate for the flow behaviour and resulting vapour generation rate, a more accurate description of the flow behaviour requires a more thorough description of the physics of phase change. However, the accuracy of this detailed description is entirely dependent on the accuracy of the implemented closures. Such models incorporate the various subprocesses observed in flash evaporation. [11, 28, 29, 30]

- **Nucleation** governs the number and spatial distribution of bubbles in the fluid. Heated walls are particularly prone to serve as nucleation sites due to the lower threshold of activation energy required. This nucleation can be modelled through the domain as homogeneous or heterogeneous - where nucleation sites are modelled using a presumed PDF function or be determined by empirical correlations. This also serves as the first estimation of the interfacial area available for mass and energy exchange.
- **Bubble Dynamics** is crucial in calculating the total interfacial area available for energy and mass exchange. After formation of a stable bubble nucleus, the growth process influences the bubble diameter at detachment and interphase energy and mass transfer rates. Bubbles can be modeled as either monodisperse with a constant radius or an estimated growth rate, or as polydisperse with varying radii. Growth of ideal spherical bubbles in uniformly superheated liquids forms the basis of the estimation of bubble growth rates. This growth rate is dependent on the surface energy and the rate of interphase energy exchange. Any relative motion between the bubble and the encasing liquid, along with inter-bubble interactions greatly influence bubble growth rate.
- **Vapour Generation Rate** can be modelled through pre-existing empirical correlations or the usage of rate equations. With increasing complexity, it can be estimated through the physics-based models accounting for nucleation, bubble dynamics, and interfacial mass and energy transfer.

2.1.2 Effects of low pressure and gravity conditions

The absence of significant gravitational forces alters the dynamics of vaporisation - affecting natural convection, buoyancy driven phenomenon, and bubble dynamics. Under terrestrial gravity, convection currents develop under thermal gradients, thus bringing cooler liquid to the heated surface as the vapour bubble rises due to buoyancy. This density driven natural convection is affected in low gravity conditions, maintaining the thermal gradient. Bulk fluid movement is affected and heat and mass transfer processes shift from being convection dominated to being diffusion dominated. [31, 32]

In nucleate boiling under low gravity conditions, vapour bubbles tend to remain near the heat source, growing significantly larger and coalescing with smaller bubbles. Prolonged bubble presence on the surface results in drying out of the surface and unsteady rise in surface temperatures during nucleate boiling[33]. In conditions where the dominance of surface tension forces becomes more pronounced, the surface tension gradients can induce fluid circulation. This is known as Marangoni convection and is observed to affect bubble growth and heat transfer. Recent experiments studying stationary volatile drop evaporation in microgravity report a 56% reduction in evaporation rate as compared to normal gravity conditions. [34, 35]

Reduced system pressure impacts the overall intensity of heat transfer. The onset of nucleate boiling also requires higher superheat values in low pressure conditions. Decrease in pressure leads to a lower number of active nucleation sites and increases microlayer thickness found at the bubble-wall interface. A decreased amount of bulk nucleation is reported along with the increased relevance of bubble growth. An overprediction is vapour mass generation is reported since large bubbles decrease the interfacial area density. [36, 37, 38]

2.2 Modelling Flash Evaporation

Rapid phase-change phenomena such as flash evaporation, boiling, and cavitation are driven by temperature or pressure drops that push the liquid into metastability beyond the saturation boundary. While boiling involves sustained heat transfer at a heated surface, the other two phenomena are pressure driven. However, these processes differ significantly in their characteristics: cavitation exhibits violent bubble collapse, whereas flash evaporation displays explosive nucleation followed by sustained vapour generation.

Nucleation

The thermodynamics of phase stability provide the foundational framework for understanding flash evaporation. Phase transition starts with random molecular aggregation that forms a 'nucleus' due to density fluctuations. This nucleus possesses the proper-

Figure 5: Initial nucleation in a bulk of superheated liquid, followed by the subsequent bubble growth turning to explosive boiling and further nucleation.

ties of the new phase. Treating a vapour nucleus as a sphere of radius R_b surrounded by a superheated liquid, the free-energy change ΔG required to form this nucleus is given by the sum of volumetric and surface contributions.

$$\Delta G = \hat{N}_v(\hat{g}_v - \hat{g}_l) + 4\pi R_b^2 \sigma - \frac{4}{3}\pi R_b^3(p_v - p_l). \quad (2.2)$$

Mechanical and thermal equilibrium expected at the critical radius R^* requires the equilibrium of the chemical potentials of the two phases and the Young-Laplace equation be satisfied. Using the following results,

$$\hat{g}_v = \hat{g}_l, \quad (2.3a)$$

$$p_v - p_l = \frac{2\sigma}{R^*}, \quad (2.3b)$$

Eqn. (2.2) reduces to the free-energy barrier,

$$\Delta G^* = 4\pi(R^*)^2\sigma - \frac{4}{3}\pi(R^*)^3\left(\frac{2\sigma}{R^*}\right) = \frac{4}{3}\pi(R^*)^2\sigma = \frac{16\pi\sigma^3}{3(p_l - p_v)^2}, \quad (2.4)$$

for the formation of stable nuclei. The nuclei exist in an unstable equilibrium where an infinitesimal increase or decrease in the radius R^* leads to a spontaneous growth or collapse respectively. This stochasticity is represented in the rate of homogeneous nucleation of vapour nuclei in superheated liquid as described using the classical nucleation theory

$$J = J_0 \exp\left(-\frac{\Delta G^*}{k_B T}\right), \quad (2.5)$$

where k_B is the Boltzmann constant. Heterogeneous nucleation can be described in the fluid bulk using a correction term added to the Eqn. (2.5). Nucleation along liquid-solid interfaces require further knowledge about the wall surface and its influence

in the lowering of the free-energy barrier. An extensive discussion of phase stability, the thermodynamic and kinetic aspects of nucleation, and subsequent derivations for homogeneous and heterogeneous nucleation can be found in [9, 10].

In computational modelling, nucleation is either accounted for through balance equations or simplified by bypassing the metastable liquid state preceding flash evaporation. Further simplifications may assume constant nucleus density, though real systems involve complex interactions between bulk-heterogeneous nucleation from impurities, surface nucleation, and homogeneous nucleation occurring simultaneously.

Bubble Growth

Once nucleation occurs and bubbles exceed the critical radius, the subsequent growth dynamics become crucial for understanding the overall phase-change process. Considering an ideal spherical bubble expanding in a uniformly superheated liquid, the growth rate is dependent upon the the surface tension, liquid inertia, and the difference in pressures inside and outside the bubble.

This idealised growth can be casted as a moving interface by solving transient conduction in the surrounding superheated liquid and enforcing the interfacial energy balance (Stefan condition) to convert heat flux into phase-change rate at the bubble surface. A solution to the Stefan problem results in the equation for calculating heat flow at the interface,

$$q(t) \Big|_{x(t)} = \frac{k_l \Delta T}{\sqrt{\alpha t}} \frac{\lambda}{St}, \quad (2.6)$$

where k_l and α_l are the thermal conductivity and diffusivity of the liquid respectively. ΔT is the temperature difference between the liquid and vapour phase and St is the dimensionless Stefan number which characterises the amount of superheat. Using the specific heat at constant pressure for the liquid $C_{p,l}$ and the latent heat of evaporation h_{lv} ,

$$St = \frac{C_{p,l}(T_l - T_v)}{h_{lv}}. \quad (2.7)$$

The thermal diffusivity α_l is defined using the specific heat, thermal conductivity and the density, $\alpha_l = k_l/(\rho_l C_{p,l})$. The determination of λ and a discussion of the Stefan problem is present in Section 4.1. [9, 39, 40]

The Rayleigh-Plesset equation Eqn. (2.8) describes the growth of the bubble of radius R_b in an infinite body of superheated liquid. The equation assumes constant liquid density and viscosity, ρ_l and ν_l , and that the pressure p_v and temperature T_v in the bubble are homogeneous. Using the external pressure p_∞ far away from the bubble, the bubble growth is described using

$$\frac{p_v(T_v) - p_\infty(t)}{\rho_l} = R_b \frac{\partial^2 R_b}{\partial t^2} + \frac{3}{2} \left(\frac{\partial R_b}{\partial t} \right)^2 + \frac{4\nu_l}{R_b} \frac{dR_b}{dt} + \frac{2\sigma}{\rho_l R_b}. \quad (2.8)$$

During the initial inertially driven growth, the vapour inside the bubble is assumed to be at saturation, thus $T_v = T_1$ and $p_v(T_v) = p_{\text{sat}}(T_1)$. Growth is maintained through the liquid superheat and is given as

$$\frac{dR_b}{dt} = \sqrt{\frac{2(p_{\text{sat}}(T_1) - p_l)}{3\rho_l}}. \quad (2.9)$$

At later stages, growth driven by heat transfer assumes that the pressure inside the bubble equals the surrounding liquid pressure, while the temperature in the bubble equals the saturation temperature at the liquid pressure. This thermally limited growth is described using energy flux absorbed as a result of phase transition. As both T_v and p_v are constant, the density can be assumed to be constant. Using Eqn. (2.6) and a thin-boundary layer assumption, the growth rate for a spherical bubble is described using the heat flux at the interface q_{lv} as,

$$h_{lv}\rho_v(T_{\text{sat}}(p_l)) \frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{4}{3} \pi R_b^3 \right) = -4\pi R_b^2 q_{lv}, \quad (2.10)$$

$$\implies \frac{dR_b}{dt} = \frac{\rho_l C_{p,l} (T_1 - T_{\text{sat}}(p_l))}{\rho_v h_{lv}} \sqrt{\frac{3\alpha_l}{\pi t}}. \quad (2.11)$$

The ratio of sensible heat in the liquid to the latent heat required for phase change is represented by the Jakob number Ja which is related to the Stefan number by the ratio of densities,

$$Ja = \frac{\rho_l C_{p,l} |T_1 - T_{\text{sat}}(p_l)|}{\rho_v h_{lv}} = \frac{\rho_l}{\rho_v} St. \quad (2.12)$$

Modifications based on the two limiting cases can be implemented as in [41], where the inertially- limiting case can be extended by superposing the thermally-limiting case as follows:

$$\frac{dR_b}{dt} = \sqrt{\frac{2(p_{\text{sat}}(T_1) - p_l)}{3\rho_l}} + \frac{\rho_l C_{p,l} |\Delta T|}{\rho_v L_{lv}} \sqrt{\frac{3}{\pi t} \left(\frac{\kappa_l}{\rho_l C_{p,l}} \right)}. \quad (2.13)$$

While in real-world situations, relative motion between bubbles and liquid or inter-bubble interactions influence growth rates, these effects are negligible under the low-pressure and low-gravity conditions of the present experiment. The classical theories are also insufficient to describe explosive boiling. Fast interface processes exhibit non-equilibrium molecular effects and the limiting factor to phase change is not only nucleation and bubble growth rates, but also mass transfer between the phases due to kinetic theory considerations.

Kinetic Effects in Non-equilibrium Phase Change

Under rapid non-equilibrium phase change, the rate of mass transfer is limited by the rate at which molecules can physically escape the liquid surface. This is particularly true in low-pressure, high-superheat conditions. Derived from the kinetic theory of

gases, the Hertz-Knudsen equation links the mass-transfer rate across the interface to the physical properties of the two phases.

Assuming a plane liquid-vapour interface and the influx of molecules in the vapour phase representing a Maxwellian distribution with a net bulk velocity, the Schrage extension to the Hertz-Knudsen equation represents the interphase mass flux as,

$$\dot{m} = \frac{2\sigma_c}{2 - \sigma_c} \sqrt{\frac{M}{2\pi RT_{sat}}} (P_{sat}(T_l) - P_v). \quad (2.14)$$

This equation describes the net mass flux, \dot{m} , as a function of the pressure difference between the saturated pressure at the liquid temperature, $P_{sat}(T_l)$, and the actual vapour pressure in the bulk, P_v . The equation is modified by the evaporation/condensation coefficient, σ_c , which accounts for the fraction of molecules that successfully cross the interface. The term under the square root represents a thermal velocity scale for the vapour molecules, where M is the molar mass and R is the universal gas constant. This formulation highlights that at low pressures and high superheat, the rate of evaporation is not only limited by heat transfer, but also by the finite speed of molecular movement across the interface.

2.3 Liquid-Vapour Multiphase Flows

Directly solving local instantaneous governing equations throughout the entire domain for multiphase flows is computationally challenging, necessitating dimensional reduction via macroscopic formulations. For two-phase flows (used interchangeably with multiphase flows), these formulations rely on averaging local flow field fluctuations while preserving continuum mechanics principles.

We denote variables associated with the liquid and vapour phases by the subscript $indi \in \{l, v\}$, respectively. Considering the classical continuum mechanics depiction of a region Ω where the two phases occupy time-dependent subregions $\Omega_l(t)$ and $\Omega_v(t)$, with $\Omega = \Omega_l(t) \cup \Omega_v(t)$ constant in time. The domain boundaries $\partial\Omega_l$, $\partial\Omega_v$, and $\partial\Omega$ define the phase interface as

$$X(t)(t) = (\partial\Omega_l \cap \partial\Omega_v) \setminus \partial\Omega. \quad (2.15)$$

Eulerian averaging is performed by keeping space and time variables constant while averaging instantaneous local variables. Volume averaging considers a representative volume element V bounded by ∂V , while time averaging applies over intervals at fixed spatial points (\bar{x}, t) . The averaging volume V is partitioned into phase volumes V_i with volume fractions

$$\alpha_i(\bar{x}, t) = \frac{V_i}{V}, \quad \alpha_l + \alpha_v = 1. \quad (2.16)$$

These averaging procedures commonly use a phase indicator function γ_i that marks phase presence within the averaging volume. The volume average of any scalar or vector quantity ψ for phase i is defined as [4, 42]

$$\overline{\psi}_i^V = \frac{1}{V} \int_V \gamma_i \psi_i(\bar{\mathbf{x}}, t) dV, \tag{2.17}$$

and the phase-intrinsic average is

$$\overline{\psi}_i^i = \frac{1}{V_i} \int_{V_i} \psi(\bar{\mathbf{x}}, t) dV = \frac{\overline{\psi}_i^V}{\alpha_i}. \tag{2.18}$$

Substituting instantaneous variables with their averaged counterparts acts as a low-pass filter, smoothing out interface discontinuities but removing direct interface topology information. This necessitates closure models for the averaged variables and lost interfacial details. While STAR-CCM+ employs Euler-averaged equations for its multiphase models, the software documentation leaves the specific averaging approach (time, volume, or a combination) open. A compact and thorough discussion on the averaging procedures can be found [43] and [44, 42, 45]. The development of the two-fluid model and one-fluid model for two-phase flows is detailed [4] and [46] respectively.

Figure 6: Flowchart summarising derivation steps for macroscopic two-phase flow formulations, differentiating one-fluid and two-fluid approaches.

Macroscopic formulations for multiphase flows can treat each phase separately or consider the mixture as a whole. The two-fluid formulation solves averaged governing

equations for each phase independently, coupled through interfacial transfer terms. Alternatively, summing the equations yields mixture behaviour, with relevant mixture constitutive terms describing the physical properties of the mixture and interfacial transfers between the phases. [4, 43, 46, 5].

Often a one-fluid model is used for its computational efficiency and ease of implementation. It generally assumes no relative velocity between phases, treating them as a single fluid with variable properties that change abruptly at the interface. This is analogous to the homogenous mixture formulation of two-phase flow. Interface-capturing methods such as volume-of-fluid (VOF) employ the one-fluid formulation along with an advected tracking function to geometrically reconstruct the interface [47, 46, 42, 7].

The following discussion assumes the averaging has been performed and considers the governing equations in their averaged macroscopic form as implemented in STAR-CCM+, assuming continuum hypothesis validity, infinitely thin interfaces, and neglecting intermolecular forces.

2.3.1 The One-Fluid Formulation

To represent two-phase flow as a single fluid with varying material properties, mixture properties are defined over the volume element V . Mixture density ρ , viscosity μ , and thermal conductivity k are volume fraction-weighted sums of the phase intrinsic averages:

$$\rho = \sum_i \alpha_i \rho_i, \quad \mu = \sum_i \alpha_i \mu_i, \quad k = \sum_i \alpha_i k_i. \quad (2.19)$$

Similarly, mixture velocity \bar{v} , specific heat C_p , and enthalpy H are mass-averaged:

$$\bar{v} = \sum_i \alpha_i \rho_i \bar{v}_i / \rho, \quad C_p = \sum_i \alpha_i C_{p,i} \rho_i / \rho, \quad H = \sum_i \alpha_i \rho_i H_i / \rho + |\bar{v}|^2 / 2, \quad (2.20)$$

where \bar{v} is the mixture velocity.

The diffusion velocity for phase i is its velocity relative to the mixture and can be used to account for relative motion between the phases,

$$\bar{v}_{d,i} = \bar{v}_i - \bar{v}. \quad (2.21)$$

Including molecular and turbulent stresses via the stress tensor $\bar{\mathbf{T}}$, the mass, momentum, and energy conservation equations in the one-fluid formulation are expressed in integral form over V as shown in equations Eqn. (2.22), Eqn. (2.23), and Eqn. (2.24). The mass, momentum, and energy sources for the phase i are denoted using S_i^α , \bar{S}_i^α , and S_i^E respectively.

Mass conservation:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \int_V \rho \, dV + \oint_{\partial V} \rho \bar{v} \cdot d\bar{a} = \int_V \sum_i S_i^\alpha \, dV. \quad (2.22)$$

Momentum conservation:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \int_V \rho \bar{\mathbf{v}} \, dV + \oint_{\partial V} \rho \bar{\mathbf{v}} \otimes \bar{\mathbf{v}} \cdot d\bar{\mathbf{a}} &= \oint_{\partial V} \left(-p\bar{\mathbf{1}} + \bar{\mathbf{T}} \right) \cdot d\bar{\mathbf{a}} + \int_V \rho \bar{\mathbf{g}} \, dV + \int_V \bar{\mathbf{f}}_b \, dV \\ &- \sum_i \oint_{\partial V} \alpha_i \rho_i \bar{\mathbf{v}}_{d,i} \otimes \bar{\mathbf{v}}_{d,i} \cdot d\bar{\mathbf{a}} + \int_V \sum_i \bar{\mathbf{S}}_i^\alpha \, dV. \end{aligned} \quad (2.23)$$

Energy conservation:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \int_V \rho E \, dV + \oint_{\partial V} \left[\rho H \bar{\mathbf{v}} + \sum_i \alpha_i \rho_i H_i \bar{\mathbf{v}}_{d,i} \right] \cdot d\bar{\mathbf{a}} &= - \oint_{\partial V} \bar{\mathbf{q}}'' \cdot d\bar{\mathbf{a}} \\ &+ \oint_{\partial V} \bar{\mathbf{T}} \cdot \bar{\mathbf{v}} \, d\bar{\mathbf{a}} + \int_V \bar{\mathbf{f}}_b \cdot \bar{\mathbf{v}} \, dV + \int_V \sum_i S_i^E \, dV. \end{aligned} \quad (2.24)$$

While computationally efficient, the one-fluid model faces challenges due to phase coupling and complex interfacial dynamics. Jump conditions are not explicitly enforced, requiring added interfacial terms which introduce numerical difficulties. modelling phase change typically involves source terms in volume fraction and energy equations [48, 46]. Many one-fluid formulations are analytically inconsistent under vaporization, failing to fully recover momentum and energy jump conditions [49].

2.3.2 The Two-Fluid Formulation

In the two-fluid formulation, the volume fractions α_i satisfy

$$\sum_i \alpha_i = 1, \quad (2.25)$$

and the phase volume is

$$V_i = \int_V \alpha_i \, dV. \quad (2.26)$$

The ratio V_i/V of the effective volume of the phase i to the total volume is defined as the void fraction of the phase.

The averaged macroscopic equation for the conservation of mass is given in Eqn. (2.27). The density and velocity of the phase i is denoted by ρ_i and $\bar{\mathbf{v}}_i$. The interfacial mass transfer unit volume between the two phases is denoted by Γ and the surface area vector of the volume element is denoted by $\bar{\mathbf{a}}$. With an additional phase mass source term S_i^α , the conservation of mass for a generic phase i is

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \int_V \alpha_i \rho_i \, dV + \oint_{\partial V} \alpha_i \rho_i \bar{\mathbf{v}}_i \cdot d\bar{\mathbf{a}} = \int_V \Gamma_i \, dV + \int_V S_i^\alpha \, dV. \quad (2.27)$$

The governing equation for the conservation of momentum is given in Eqn. (2.28). The equation describes the change in momentum of the phase i due to the effects of the fundamental forces in the system along with the effects of any internal forces or potentials $(\bar{\mathbf{F}}_{\text{int}})_i$ or any phase momentum source terms $\bar{\mathbf{S}}_i^\alpha$. The pressure and gravitational acceleration are given as p and $\bar{\mathbf{g}}$ respectively. The stress tensor $\bar{\mathbf{T}}_i$ comprises the molecular and turbulent stress tensors. Turbulence is addressed in Section 2.4.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \int_V \alpha_i \rho_i \bar{\mathbf{v}}_i \, dV + \oint_{\partial V} \alpha_i \rho_i \bar{\mathbf{v}}_i \otimes \bar{\mathbf{v}}_i \cdot d\bar{\mathbf{a}} = \int_V (-\alpha_i \nabla p + \alpha_i \rho_i \bar{\mathbf{g}} + (\bar{\mathbf{F}}_{\text{int}})_i) \, dV \\ + \oint_{\partial V} [\alpha_i (\bar{\mathbf{T}}_i)] \cdot d\bar{\mathbf{a}} + \int_V \bar{\mathbf{S}}_i^\alpha \, dV + \int_V (\Gamma_i \bar{\mathbf{v}}_i + \bar{\mathcal{M}}_i) \, dV. \end{aligned} \quad (2.28)$$

The momentum transfer term $\bar{\mathcal{M}}_i$ accounts for the momentum transfer from the phase i to the interface. This term also accounts for the momentum transfer due to interfacial mass transfer and is further detailed in Section 3.2. It is only non-zero in case of a relative motion between the phases and is subject to the constraint.

The averaged macroscopic formulation of the conservation of energy in the two-fluid formulation is shown in Eqn. (2.29). The equation accounts for the change of the total energy E_i in the volume V due to the work done by line, surface, and volume (body) forces on the volume element, any heat transfer (in this specific case, only conduction and convection are considered), and due to the interfacial mass transfer in the volume element.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \int_V \alpha_i \rho_i E_i \, dV + \oint_{\partial V} \alpha_i \rho_i H_i \bar{\mathbf{v}}_i \cdot d\bar{\mathbf{a}} = \oint_{\partial V} \alpha_i (k_{\text{eff}})_i \nabla T_i \cdot d\bar{\mathbf{a}} + \oint_{\partial V} \bar{\mathbf{T}}_i \bar{\mathbf{v}}_i \cdot d\bar{\mathbf{a}} \\ + \int_V \bar{\mathbf{f}}_{b_i} \cdot \bar{\mathbf{v}}_i \, dV + \int_V S_{u,i} \, dV + \int_V (\Gamma_i H_i + \mathcal{E}_i) \, dV. \end{aligned} \quad (2.29)$$

The effective thermal conductivity, k_{eff} is an extension of the thermal conductivity along with turbulence contributions to it.

$$k_{\text{eff},i} = k_i + \frac{\mu_{t,i} C_{p,i}}{\sigma_{t,i}}$$

The interphase energy transfer term $\Gamma_i H_i + \mathcal{E}_i$ consists of the energy exchange due to mass transfer, and \mathcal{E}_i which consists of the interphase heat transfer rate due to temperature differences between the two phases and the rate of heat transfer from the phase i to the interface. Interphase heat transfer terms are modelled using the Newton's law of cooling and are represented by the heat transfer coefficient, the interfacial area concentration, and the temperature difference. [7]

The total energy E_i is related to the total enthalpy H_i

$$E_i = H_i - \frac{p}{\rho_i}$$

and the total enthalpy to the sensible enthalpy such as,

$$\begin{aligned} H_i &= h_i(T_i) + \frac{1}{2} \mathbf{v}_i \cdot \mathbf{v}_i \\ &= h_i^{\text{REF}} + \int_{T_i^{\text{REF}}}^{T_i} C_{p,i}(T') dT' + \frac{1}{2} \mathbf{v}_i \cdot \mathbf{v}_i. \end{aligned} \quad (2.30)$$

By explicitly balancing transfer processes for each phase, the two-fluid formulation offers a more complete and general two-phase flow description. It captures dynamic and non-equilibrium phase interactions but requires closure models for interphase exchanges. Neither the mixture nor two-fluid models retain interface topology information and cannot specify flow regimes based solely on void fraction [4].

2.3.3 Interfacial Jump Conditions

Jump conditions are the kinematic and dynamic conditions that account for the discontinuities in material properties or flow variables across an interface and couple the behaviour of the two fluids across it.

The interfacial mass transfer term Γ_i in Eqn. (2.27) represents the rate of mass transfer from the phase i . The interaction area density a_{lv} specifies the interfacial area available in the volume element over which the mass transfer occurs. Globally the sum $\sum \Gamma_i$ must be equal to zero.

$$\Gamma_i = a_{lv} \dot{m}_i = \rho_i \mathbf{n}_i \cdot (\mathbf{v}_i - \mathbf{v}_{X(t)}). \quad (2.31)$$

The term $\rho_i \bar{\mathbf{n}}_i \cdot (\bar{\mathbf{v}}_i - \bar{\mathbf{v}}_{X(t)})$ consists of the local instantaneous variables instead of the averaged quantities. The interface normal vector and interface velocity are given as $\bar{\mathbf{n}}_i$ and $\bar{\mathbf{v}}_{X(t)}$ respectively.

The momentum transfer term $\Gamma_i \bar{\mathbf{v}}_i$ accounts for the momentum transfer from the phase i to j due to mass transfer. The momentum transfer to the interface is accounted through the $\bar{\mathcal{M}}_i$ term. It is only non-zero in case of a relative motion between the phases and represents the actions of the various forces coupling the phases.

$$\bar{\mathcal{M}}_i = \bar{\mathbf{F}}_{ij}^D + F_{ij}^L + F_{ij}^{VM} + F_{ij}^{TD} + F_{ij}^{WL}. \quad (2.32)$$

The right hand side in Eqn. (2.32) is composed of the interfacial drag, lift, virtual mass, turbulent dispersion, and the wall lubrication force respectively. The term $\bar{\mathcal{M}}_i$, similar to \dot{m} is weighted using the interfacial surface area a_{indlv} .

In case of constant surface tension, the dynamic condition that the effects of the hydrodynamic forces are in equilibrium with the forces due to surface tension. Denoting

the part of the interface $X(t)$ in the volume element V as $X(t) \cap V$, the dynamic jump condition can be written as

$$\bar{\mathcal{M}}_l + \bar{\mathcal{M}}_v + \sum \Gamma_i \bar{v}_i = \frac{1}{V} \int_{X(t) \cap V} \bar{f}_\sigma dV. \quad (2.33)$$

The interfacial thermal energy transfer condition satisfies the constraint

$$\sum_i (\Gamma_i H_i + \mathcal{E}_i) = 0. \quad (2.34)$$

2.4 Turbulence

Flows are generally turbulent. Turbulence is characterised by irregular fluid motion dominated by eddies and vortices across a wide range of spatial and temporal scales. The largest eddies extract kinetic energy from the mean flow, which is then, through a cascade, transferred to the eddies at the smallest scale where the energy is dissipated due to viscosity, raising the internal energy of the fluid [12, 50].

Reynolds Averaged Navier Stokes (RANS) models result from decomposing flow variables into mean and fluctuating components, $\phi = \bar{\phi} + \phi'$, applying Reynolds averaging, which filters out turbulent fluctuations below the averaging scale [51, 52]. This operation yields additional Reynolds stress terms representing momentum transport by turbulence, which require closure. In order to draw closure relations, eddy-viscosity models of turbulence assume that:

- the turbulent scalar flux vector aligns with the mean scalar gradient.
- the Reynolds stress tensor is proportional to the mean velocity strain rate through an eddy viscosity.

While simplifying turbulence modelling, these assumptions often fail to fully capture turbulence physics, especially in anisotropic or non-equilibrium flows [53]. This limitation is significant in regions with complex strain rates or strong secondary flows.

Although various turbulence models exist at different levels of resolution, no general-purpose model perfectly captures all flow scenarios. In this study, turbulence is modeled using the Shear Stress Transport (SST) $k-\omega$ model, a two-equation eddy-viscosity model based on the RANS equations.

The SST $k-\omega$ model combines the advantages of the $k-\omega$ model near walls, which accurately resolves boundary layers, and the $k-\varepsilon$ model in the free stream, enhancing robustness and accuracy especially in separated flows [54]. It uses a blending function to smoothly transition between these models, which is particularly effective in flows exhibiting strong adverse pressure gradients and separation, such as multiphase cavity flows [55]. Another blending function limits the eddy viscosity in wake regions, and a cross-diffusion term ensures consistency between the $k-\omega$ and $k-\varepsilon$ formulations.

The model defines the eddy viscosity μ_t as

$$\mu_t = \rho k T_t, \quad (2.35)$$

where T_t is the turbulent time scale defined using the model constant β^* and the dissipation rate ω . The turbulent time along with the turbulent length scale are defined as

$$T_t = \frac{1}{\beta^* \omega}. \quad (2.36)$$

Since the RANS governing equations closely resemble those described in the previous section, they are omitted here for brevity. The implemented set of equations can be found in the STAR-CCM+ documentation [7].

The transport equations for the turbulent kinetic energy k and the specific dissipation rate ω are given by

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \rho k + \nabla \cdot (\rho k \bar{\mathbf{v}}) = \nabla \cdot [(\mu + \sigma_k \mu_t) \nabla k] + P_k - \rho \beta^* f_{\beta^*} (\omega k - \omega_0 k_0) + S_k, \quad (2.37a)$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \rho \omega + \nabla \cdot (\rho \omega \bar{\mathbf{v}}) = \nabla \cdot [(\mu + \sigma_\omega \mu_t) \nabla \omega] + P_\omega - \rho \beta f_\beta (\omega^2 - \omega_0^2) + S_\omega, \quad (2.37b)$$

where σ_k and σ_ω are the turbulent Prandtl numbers for k and ω , respectively.

2.5 Summary

Flash evaporation is inherently non-equilibrium: accurate prediction hinges on nucleation seeding, transient interfacial area, bubble dynamics, and kinetic mass transfer - not solely on bulk heat supply. Low pressure and reduced gravity amplify kinetic and diffusion limits while suppressing buoyancy-convection, reinforcing the need for physics-based closures and, where feasible, non-homogeneous, non-equilibrium formulations. The chapter thereby motivates the later numerical choices: consistent interface jump conditions, careful turbulence treatment near phase boundaries, and closure selections that remain transferable beyond case-specific tuning.

3 Computational Methodology

This chapter documents the numerical framework in STAR-CCM+, detailing the one-fluid VOF method for separated free surfaces and the Eulerian Multiphase model with Large-Scale Interface capabilities for regime-spanning applications. It explains interface-capturing, 2D adaptive remeshing to sharpen fronts, and the closure palette for surface tension using the continuum surface theory, interfacial momentum (drag, lift, turbulent dispersion, wall lubrication), and interphase heat transfer. Finally, it states modeling assumptions and boundary conditions for both infiltration and the envisioned flashing application.

3.1 Multiphase-Flows in STAR-CCM+

STAR-CCM+ employs a finite-volume, cell-centered scheme with variables stored at cell centroids and interpolated to faces, using second-order upwind for convection, least-squares gradients with Venkatakrishnan limiting, and the Semi-Implicit Method for Pressure Linked Equations (SIMPLE) scheme for segregated pressure-velocity coupling. This ensures a balance of accuracy, boundedness, and robustness in the presence of large density jumps and under-resolved interfaces. Interface-capturing methods necessarily produce a minimum interface thickness of a few cells, motivating bounded convective schemes and careful limiter usage to control numerical diffusion and spurious currents. RANS modeling is used with the SST $k - \omega$ model, realizability controls, turbulence intensity and length-scale boundary specification, and optional quadratic/cubic stress-strain relations for anisotropy in flows with strong secondary motions

At large scale interfaces, the near-interface flow often exhibits laminar characteristics with the development of boundary layers. However, in situations with significant velocity gradients, turbulent fluctuations can arise in the regions adjacent to the interface (especially when the interface is mobile or highly distorted). Recognizing that standard RANS turbulence models tend to overpredict turbulence intensity near phase boundaries, STAR-CCM+ allows the user to apply turbulence damping strategies (vorticity limiters) which suppress excessive eddy viscosity and restore physically consistent laminar sublayers adjacent to the interface.

3.1.1 Volume-of-Fluid Method

The volume-of-fluid (VOF) method is an interface capturing method that utilises the governing equations of the one-fluid model as detailed in Section 2.3.1. The method presumes that the computational mesh is fine enough to resolve the interface topology. Using the volume fraction as the marker function - the interface is assumed to be

present in cells with volume fraction values between 0 and 1. The distribution of the phase i is driven by the volume fraction transport equation,

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \int_V \alpha_i dV + \oint_{\partial V} \alpha_i \bar{\mathbf{v}}_i \cdot d\bar{\mathbf{a}} = \int_V \left(S_i^\alpha - \frac{\alpha_i}{\rho_i} \frac{D\rho_i}{Dt} \right) dV - \int_V \frac{1}{\rho_i} \nabla \cdot (\alpha_i \rho_i \bar{\mathbf{v}}_{d,i}) dV. \quad (3.1)$$

In case of two phases, the volume fraction transport is solved only for the first phase, thus in each volume element, the volume fraction of phase j is given as $\alpha_j = 1 - \alpha_i$.

For convection of volume fraction, STAR-CCM+ employs a modified High-Resolution Interface Capturing (HRIC) scheme that blends downwind and upwind via normalized-variable diagrams with Courant-number corrections to preserve boundedness and sharpness. The spurious oscillations that may arise in the volume fraction field due to meshes with large aspect ratios are suppressed by artificially smoothing the volume fraction gradient across the interface. [7]

3.1.2 Eulerian Multiphase Method

Star-CCM+ implements the governing equations of the two-fluid model as detailed in Section 2.3.2 as the eulerian multiphase (EMP) model. The two-fluid model is predominantly used to simulate dispersed flows and the mesh resolution is assumed to be coarse enough to not capture the interface topology between the phases. The EMP model, however, utilises the multiple flow regime framework to allow the simulation of multiscale flows. Based on increasing volume fraction of the secondary phase, α_s , in a finite volume cell, the topology transitions through three principal regimes [47, 7], where the secondary phase is:

- dispersed in the primary phase (first dispersed regime, $0 \leq \alpha_s \leq \alpha_{fr}$)
- separated from the primary phase through a large scale interface (interfacial flow regime, $\alpha_{fr} \leq \alpha_s \leq \alpha_{sr}$)
- continuous while having the primary phase dispersed (second dispersed regime, $\alpha_{sr} \leq \alpha_s \leq 1$)

The first and second regime terminuses, α_{fr} and α_{sr} , mark the values of α_s that define the end of the first dispersed and large scale interface regimes respectively. STAR-CCM+ uses regime-specific closure models for the interfacial momentum and energy terms. These models are blended using a weighting scheme according to the calculated proportion of each regime in the cell.

Adaptive Interface Sharpening (ADIS) is used in the multiregime framework to switch to HRIC near large interfaces and revert to upwind away from interfaces, avoiding spurious sharpening in smooth regions while limiting oscillations at high aspect-ratio meshes.

3.1.3 Adaptive Mesh Refinement

STAR-CCM+ provides provisions to include adaptive mesh refinement to locally refine the mesh based on either pre-defined or user-field functions. For 2D meshes, this provision has not been included, however the Remeshing solver can be included in the solution to locally refine the mesh during the evolution of the solution. The mesh refinement is unidirectional and does not coarsen already refined regions of the mesh.

In context of this thesis, a user defined field function based on the volume fraction of water has been used in the implementation of the VOF method to refine the mesh with increasing time steps. Fig. 7 displays progressive refinements in the remeshing process as the solution evolves for the case of water flowing into a chamber.

3.2 Closures

Closures are critical to the accurate prediction of the relevant flow variables and the distribution of volume fraction [56]. Existing literature reviews the overwhelming number of closures available that yield a range of varying performance along with their comparison with experimental data, however literature presenting CFD simulations tend to choose 'result-oriented' closures that aren't transferable to a wider range of flow situations. Literature admits that the industry relies on the tunable parameters in the closures to match the specific experimental data being simulated or the arbitrariness of this choice to get improved flow predictions. [57, 58, 59]

Models may also provide satisfying predictions for certain parameters or situations while failing in others and a general incoherence prevails while discussing the effects of interfacial forces. Early work has tended to neglect the effects of lift or virtual mass forces, or chosen to use constant coefficients to describe them while using formulations for the drag forces based on relevant non-dimensional numbers. The effect of non-drag forces, however, tends to be as significant on the distribution of phases. [59]

Since it is difficult to separate the effects of the various forces in actual experiments, the development of these closures assumes certain idealisations when they're not partly or wholly based on empirical data, rendering them highly flow dependent. The methodology of resolving a complex interfacial momentum transfer through a linear superposition of several simple forces is also questioned. [56].

Closures should reflect the local physical phenomenon occurring on the non-resolved scale. But this requires a better understanding of the physics of such local flow phenomena. Consequently, the closures should reflect the physics including their dependence on material parameters and local flow characteristics. Best practices suggest that all relevant closure models should be included - if the model reflects the physics accurately, the locally unimportant closures will be blended out automatically.

Figure 7: Adaptive mesh refinement based on volume fraction of liquid as refinement criteria.

The industry has, however, attempted to establish generality that can be transferred to multiple flow situations and has proposed baseline frameworks. There is a general consensus that the role of turbulence is underestimated [60]; current models also aim to reduce uncertainty and inconsistency in model selection [60], adopt closures that avoid "case-specific adjustments to unphysical coefficients and tunable parameters" [56], and utilise more physics based closures that are more physically consistent [59, 60].

3.2.1 Surface Tension

Surface tension, although an interfacial force, is implemented using the Continuum Surface Force approach as a volumetric force in the momentum equation. [7] Divided into normal and tangential components and using the mean curvature of the free surface $\kappa = -\nabla \cdot (\nabla\alpha_i/|\nabla\alpha_i|)$, the volumetric surface tension force is given as

$$\bar{\mathbf{f}}_{\sigma} = \underbrace{-\sigma \nabla \cdot \frac{\nabla\alpha_i}{|\nabla\alpha_i|} \nabla\alpha_i}_{\bar{\mathbf{f}}_{\sigma,n}} + \underbrace{(\nabla\sigma)_t |\nabla\alpha_i|}_{\bar{\mathbf{f}}_{\sigma,t}} \quad (3.2)$$

The EMP treats surface tension by splitting it among the phases occupying the cell using the local volume fractions. The pressure gradient is then the summation of the individual phase surface tension contributions $\bar{\mathbf{f}}_{\sigma,i}$ [47, 7],

$$\bar{\mathbf{f}}_{\sigma,i} = \alpha_i \sigma \kappa \nabla\alpha_i. \quad (3.3)$$

3.2.2 Interphase Momentum Closures

Accurate interfacial momentum exchange controls phase distribution and slip, so closure choices strongly influence mean velocities and void-fraction fields.

Drag force is generally more dominant than other forces as they tend to be a magnitude higher than other forces [61]. Most drag models perform equally well at low gas volume fractions. However as they are based on ideal conditions, they do not account for bubble swarm effects at higher gas volume fractions and show reduced accuracy. Certain swarm corrections do exist, but they are averaged along a radial profile when the swarm effects are also felt in the bulk [56, 58, 60]. The accurate modelling of interaction area density and length becomes relevant for the calculation of the drag force. Using the linearised drag coefficient, A_D , and the relative velocity between the phases $\bar{\mathbf{v}}_r = \bar{\mathbf{v}}_j - \bar{\mathbf{v}}_i$, STAR-CCM+ implements the drag force as,

$$\bar{\mathbf{F}}_{ij}^D = A_D \bar{\mathbf{v}}_r \quad (3.4)$$

The linearised drag coefficient is related to the standard definitions of the drag coefficient C_D using

$$A_D = C_D \frac{1}{2} \rho_c |\bar{\mathbf{v}}_r| \frac{a_{cd}}{4} \quad (3.5)$$

where a_{cd} is the interfacial area density and $a_{cd}/4$ represents the projected area of the equivalent spherical particle.

The lift force models are particularly sensitive and uncertain in their performance [58]. They suffer from the same discrepancy between performance in low and high gas volume fractions. Moreover, existing lift force implementations in STAR-CCM+ fail to replicate the experimental data they were derived from [56]. Assuming α_p is the volume fraction of the primary (continuous) phase, STAR-CCM+ implements the lift force as

$$F_{ij}^L = C_{L,\text{eff}} \alpha_d \rho_p [\bar{\mathbf{v}}_r \times (\nabla \times \bar{\mathbf{v}}_p)]. \quad (3.6)$$

A turbulent dispersion force is supposed to act on the gas phase and spreads this dispersed phase due to turbulence in the continuous phase. This is typically modelled as a diffusion term proportional to the turbulent kinetic energy gradients [38]. The force is theorised to arise from the averaging of the fluctuations of the bubbles due to the turbulence.

$$F_{ij}^{TD} = A_D \bar{\mathbf{v}}_{TD} = A_D \underbrace{C_0 \frac{\nu_c^t}{\sigma_\alpha} \bar{\mathbf{I}}}_{\bar{\mathbf{D}}_{TD}} \cdot [\nabla \ln(\alpha_d) - \nabla \ln(\alpha_c)] \quad (3.7)$$

The closure relation by Burns [7] uses the Favre averaging of the drag force and can be expressed as

$$F_{ij}^{TD} = C_D C_{TD} \frac{\mu_l^t}{\rho_c \sigma_{TD}} \bar{\mathbf{v}}_{TD}, \quad (3.8)$$

where C_D is the drag coefficient, C_{TD} is an adjustable turbulent dispersion calibration coefficient, μ_l^t is the liquid turbulent viscosity, and σ_{TD} is the turbulent Prandtl number.

Most lift coefficient correlations don't account for the decrease of the magnitude of the lift force to zero near the walls. This low gas volume fraction at the walls has historically been explained through a liquid film forming at the walls repelling the bubbles. This has been demonstrated to not actually occur in practice. The wall lubrication force has thus been criticised as lacking any physical justification [56, 60]. Newer closures [56, 7] utilise a turbulent dispersion force based formulation to maintain the desired gas volume fraction and use the closure instead as a correction term to resolve the phase distribution at the boundary lost due to the averaging process. STAR-CCM+'s implementation of the wall lubrication force

$$F_{ij}^{WL} = -C_{WL}(y_w) \alpha_s \rho_p \frac{|\bar{\mathbf{v}}_r - (\bar{\mathbf{v}} \cdot \bar{\mathbf{n}}) \bar{\mathbf{n}}|}{d_b} \bar{\mathbf{n}} \quad (3.9)$$

can be changed to implement alternative models instead by defining user defined field functions for C_{WL} .

3.2.3 Interphase Heat Transfers

STAR-CCM+ models heat transfer by using the analogy to Newton's law of cooling. This entails the estimations of accurate heat transfer coefficient correlations that can link the liquid superheat to vapour generation in a reliable manner. This choice controls the predictive accuracy of the rate of phase change under non-equilibrium conditions. As with the case of momentum closures, there is no universally valid correlation as the law of cooling is a simplification of the actual heat transfer mechanisms in multiphase flows. A composite heat transfer coefficient correlation that accounts for the conduction- and convection-based limits can be constructed using a linear superposition of the various individual heat transfer correlations. Heat transfer through turbulence can also be similarly considered.

3.2.4 Nucleation and Interphase Transfer Closures

Homogeneous nucleation and subsequent bubble growth are not inherent to the two-fluid model's fundamental equations. To capture these effects, a scalar transport equation for the bubble number density must be solved along with the flow variables, with source terms accounting for:

1. Nucleation: A nucleation model, such as the one based on the classical nucleation theory (CNT), provides the source of new bubbles. This term depends exponentially on the liquid superheat.
2. Bubble Growth/Collapse: The growth of these newly formed bubbles is governed by interphase heat and mass transfer. The mass transfer rate is given by a model like the HKS equation, while the heat transfer rate requires a closure for the interphase heat transfer coefficient.
3. Coalescence and Breakup: To account for changes in bubble size distribution, models for bubble coalescence and breakup are also required. These models are typically empirical and depend on the local turbulence and velocity gradients. In the context of our experimental conditions, as bubbles in low gravity show lower detachment rates and grow much larger in size than in terrestrial conditions. Coalescence will dominate as growing bubbles eat each other up but do not leave the nucleating surface. This factor, due to the modelling complications can be ignored.

While a simple, pressure-driven mass transfer model like Lee model can be used to bypass these complexities, its parameters are often highly tuned and lack physical basis. The population balance approach, while more complex, provides a more fundamental and physically consistent framework for modeling two-phase flows with a changing bubble size distribution.

3.3 Model of the Experiment

The experimental flow system encompasses distinct flow regimes that differ in physical nature and complexity across its various components. To effectively capture these differences, the numerical simulation is logically divided into two subproblems: the liquid intrusion phase, characterized by transient multiphase displacement of air by water, and the subsequent evaporation phase, involving rapid phase change under vacuum conditions.

In order to establish kinematic and dynamic similarity with the experimental setup, the modelled domain is geometrically same as the actual setup. Relevant scales are defined and STAR-CCM+'s automatic assignment of a 1m depth to 2D domains is accounted for in the initial conditions for the infiltration problem and establish dynamical similarity.

It is acknowledged that the current modeling employs two-dimensional simulations predominantly for computational efficiency, which inherently introduces limitations in capturing fully three-dimensional flow structures and turbulence anisotropies present in the actual experimental setup. Similarly, the adoption of the Boussinesq approximation within the SST $k-\omega$ turbulence model introduces simplifications that neglect density variations except in buoyancy terms, potentially diminishing accuracy in regimes where density gradients or compressibility effects become significant.

Despite these simplifications and inherent approximations, the staged subproblem approach facilitates focused investigation of the dominant physical phenomena in each phase. The following subsection details the modeling setup specific to the liquid intrusion phase, outlining assumptions, governing equations, boundary conditions, and validation strategies.

3.3.1 Assumptions

We model the experiment on a 2D domain. Water is assumed to be incompressible in both the subproblems. Air is modelled as an ideal gas in the infiltration problem. All phases are assumed to be immiscible. We assume that the continuum hypothesis holds and that the macroscopic averaged quantities are smooth. We assume transport properties such as viscosity and conductivity are constant over the averaging procedure and that interfaces are infinitely thin.

It is assumed that the fundamental assumptions in eddy-viscosity modelling are true and that Reynolds stress tensor is proportional to the mean velocity strain rate through an eddy viscosity defined as in Eqn. (2.35) [7].

$$\bar{\mathbf{T}}_{\text{RANS}} = \mu_t(\nabla\bar{\mathbf{v}} + \nabla\bar{\mathbf{v}}^T) - \frac{2}{3}(\mu_t\nabla\bar{\mathbf{v}})\bar{\mathbf{I}}, \quad (3.10)$$

In cases of continuous-dispersed regimes, we assume that the interfacial shear stress is equivalent to the shear stress in the continuous phase.

In the formulation of the liquid infiltration problem, no relative velocity is considered between the phases and the diffusion velocity in Eqn. (2.21) is 0. Apart from the liquid inflow, no additional source terms are present. We assume that the heat exchanged between the environment and the boundaries of the system is dominated by conduction and prescribe a very low heat transfer coefficient to account for the heat lost to the environment. This prescription is not considered in the evaporation problem, where the system is assumed to be isolated.

3.3.2 Governing Equations and Boundary Conditions

The infiltration problem uses the governing equations for the one-fluid formulation and the evaporation equation utilises the two-fluid formulation as described in Section 2.3.1 and Section 2.3.2 respectively. As only the 2D aspects of the problem are considered, the momentum and energy equations in the z -axis directions are not solved.

Boundary Conditions: Liquid Infiltration

The jump conditions at the interface without phase change are considered based on the discussion Section 2.3.3. These are summarised below:

$$[[\bar{v}]] = 0, \quad (3.11a)$$

$$\left[\left[\left(\mu (\nabla \bar{v} + (\nabla \bar{v})^T) - (p + \rho \bar{g} \cdot \bar{x}) \bar{\mathbf{I}} \right) \cdot \bar{\mathbf{n}} \right] \right] = \sigma \kappa \bar{\mathbf{n}} + [[\rho]] \bar{\mathbf{g}}. \quad (3.11b)$$

The domain boundaries of the system are specified as walls without slip, thus fluid velocity at wall is 0. The inlet is assigned as a velocity inlet, with the velocity and temperature of the inflowing water specified.

The boundary specifications for heat transfer for the infiltration problem are summarised below:

$$\text{Walls: Convection specification,} \quad \dot{q} = h_{\text{ext}}(T_w - T_\infty), \quad (3.12a)$$

$$\text{Outlet: Adiabatic} \quad \dot{q} = 0, \quad (3.12b)$$

$$\text{Inlet: Specified temperature of infiltrating water} \quad T = T_{in}. \quad (3.12c)$$

For the specification of the wall temperature T_w is the static fluid temperature at the wall.

3.4 Summary

The chosen discretisation, advection controls, and remeshing strategy balance boundedness, interface sharpness, and stability in the presence of large density jumps and

moving free surfaces. While the approach is assumed to be pragmatic, closure selections and additional damping options aim to mitigate known artifacts near phase boundaries, enabling credible verification tests and a setup applicable for the simulation of the infiltration problem.

4 Numerical Results

This chapter outlines the computational setup and results for simulating the liquid infiltration into the evaporation chamber. The employed models are first validated against classical benchmark problems - the 1D Stefan problem and the 2D Rayleigh-Taylor instability - to ensure credibility of the numerical approach. The Stefan problem benchmarks energy conservation and interface motion against the analytical solution, and Rayleigh-Taylor simulations reproduce canonical interfacial roll-up and mixing trends observed in two-phase flows. A concise overview of the methodologies and results for these benchmarks are followed by discussion of the infiltration simulations in the experimental geometry. The infiltration study, built with adaptive remeshing, quantifies free-surface evolution, velocity fields, and probe-based pressure/temperature histories in the chamber and nozzle, yielding consistent end-of-injection states that can be used to initialise the flashing phase.

4.1 Stefan Problem

Phase change processes are characterised by the motion of an interface separating two distinct phases, where heat transfer governs the interface displacement according to conservation of energy principles [62].

In the classical Stefan problem, a prescribed temperature boundary propagates a melting or freezing front, with the interface movement determined by the balance of latent heat and conducted heat [63]. Assuming uniform initial temperature, constant boundary temperature, and homogeneous thermophysical properties in each phase, the semi-infinite one-dimensional Stefan problem represents the simplest analytically solvable phase change model. It admits an analytical solution, reducing to the standard transient conduction problem when latent heat is neglected, thereby serving as a benchmark for verifying phase-change models and the proper implementation of the energy equation. [63, 64, 65]

In context of this study, the moving-interface heat-balance problem encountered in the Stefan problem is analogous to the growth of a spherical vapour bubble in superheated liquid in late stages. The interface normal velocity is constrained by the interfacial mass flux through density and latent heat - emphasising the thermal diffusion controlled growth.

Consider a semi-infinite rectangular domain $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^2$:

$$\Omega = \{(x, y) \in \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R} : x \in [0, \infty), y \in [0, \Delta h]\},$$

partitioned into solid and liquid subregions Ω_s and Ω_l , with $\Omega = \Omega_s \cup \Omega_l$. The interface location is defined by $X(t)$, and $\partial\Omega$ denotes the boundary of Ω .

Figure 8: Problem setup

The temperature field $T(x, t)$ in the liquid phase satisfies the heat equation coupled with the Stefan condition at the interface. The system reads:

$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = \alpha \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x^2}, \quad 0 < x < X(t) \quad t_0 < t < t_f, \quad (4.1a)$$

$$-k \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} \Big|_{x=X(t)^-} = \rho L \frac{dX}{dt}, \quad t_0 < t < t_f, \quad (4.1b)$$

$$T(x, 0) = T_m \quad x \in \Omega \quad (4.1c)$$

$$T(0, t) = T_l \quad t_0 < t < t_f \quad (4.1d)$$

$$\nabla T \cdot \bar{\mathbf{n}} = 0 \quad \text{on } \partial\Omega \setminus \{x = 0\} \quad (4.1e)$$

where α is the thermal diffusivity, k the thermal conductivity, ρ the density, L the latent heat, and $\bar{\mathbf{n}}$ the outward normal on $\partial\Omega$.

The one-dimensional analytical solution to Eqn. (4.1) is given by:

$$T(x, t) = T_l - (T_l - T_m) \frac{\operatorname{erf}\left(\frac{x}{2\sqrt{\alpha t}}\right)}{\operatorname{erf}\left(\frac{X(t)}{2\sqrt{\alpha t}}\right)}, \quad X(t) = 2\lambda\sqrt{\alpha t}, \quad (4.2)$$

where λ is determined as the unique root of

$$f(\lambda) := \frac{C_p(T_m - T_l)}{L} - \frac{\lambda e^{-\lambda^2}}{\sqrt{\pi} \operatorname{erf}(\lambda)} = 0,$$

with C_p the specific heat and $\operatorname{erf}(\cdot)$ the error function:

$$\operatorname{erf}(z) := \frac{2}{\sqrt{\pi}} \int_0^z \exp(-y^2) dy.$$

The computational domain used to model the Stefan problem in STAR-CCM+ is a two-dimensional rectangular region with dimensions $L_x = 0.5$ m in the horizontal direction and $6\Delta h = 3.0 \times 10^{-3}$ m in the vertical direction, where $\Delta h = 5.0 \times 10^{-4}$ m denotes the base mesh size.

A trimmed cell mesher is used to discretize the domain into quadrilateral cells with uniform size Δh . No mesh refinement or alignment is applied to maintain mesh uniformity.

The simulation models a melting-solidification process using a single-phase, constant-density fluid with laminar energy transport. The fluid phase loosely corresponds to water (H_2O) with constant density $\rho = 1000 \text{ kg/m}^3$, specific heat $c_p = 4200 \text{ J kg}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$, and a temperature-dependent thermal conductivity switching between solid and liquid values via a user-defined scalar field function. The latent heat of fusion is set to $h_m = 1.0 \times 10^5 \text{ J kg}^{-1}$, and the melting temperature $T_m = 273 \text{ K}$.

The VOF model with a modified High-Resolution Interface Capturing (HRIC) convection scheme is employed to track the phase interface. The melting-solidification coupling is activated to model latent heat effects during phase change.

Boundary conditions include no-slip velocity constraints on all walls. The upper and lower boundaries are adiabatic, while a fixed temperature condition $T_L = 300 \text{ K}$ is applied on one vertical wall to induce melting. The initial temperature throughout the domain is uniform and set to the melting temperature $T_m = 273 \text{ K}$, with zero initial velocity.

Solver settings apply the segregated flow solver with SIMPLE pressure-velocity coupling. Temporal discretization utilizes an implicit first-order time-stepping scheme with a fixed time step $\Delta t = 0.5 \text{ s}$. Relaxation factors are set conservatively to maintain numerical stability.

Simulation output includes temperature fields, solid volume fraction, and interface location, extracted periodically for validation against the analytical solution. The simulation runs until a maximum physical time of $t_{\max} = 1000 \text{ s}$.

Table 1 summarises the key physical properties and numerical methods employed. The temperature field evolution for a simulation with mesh size $\Delta h = 5.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ m}$ is shown in Fig. 9. The phase interface advances towards the positive x -direction over time. Temperature decreases from the Dirichlet boundary at $x = 0$ towards the melting temperature T_m at the interface, remaining constant beyond.

Fig. 11 compares the numerically predicted interface location for different mesh sizes against the analytical solution. The interface position is inferred by combining volume fraction and temperature data. Data are sampled at 100 s intervals. The absolute interface location error is displayed in Fig. 11a. The numerical temperature profiles are quantified against the analytical solution through the L_2 and L_∞ norms:

$$L_2 = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (T_i - T_{\text{analytical},i})^2}, \quad L_\infty = \max_i |T_i - T_{\text{analytical},i}|.$$

Figure 9: Evolution of the phase change interface over time.

Figure 10: Location of the phase change interface versus time.

Simulation Setup	
Domain	Two-dimensional rectangular
Mesh size, Δh	2.0×10^{-3} m
Time discretization	Implicit unsteady, first-order Euler
Time step, Δt	0.5 s
Physical Properties	
Density, ρ	1000.0 kg m^{-3}
Dynamic viscosity, μ	8.8871×10^{-4} Pa s
Specific heat, C_p	$4200.0 \text{ J kg}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$
Latent heat of fusion, L	$1.0 \times 10^5 \text{ J kg}^{-1}$
Thermal conductivity (liquid), k_l	$2.33 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$
Thermal conductivity (solid), k_s	$0.62 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$
Melting temperature, T_m	273 K
Numerical Methods	
Multiphase model	VOF with first-order HRIC convection scheme
Flow regime	Laminar
Discretisation Scheme	Second-order upwind (energy), blended second- and first-order upwind (volume fraction)

Table 1: Simulation parameters and physics models for the Stefan melting-solidification problem.

Temperature error decreases with mesh refinement, as shown in Fig. 11b, confirming convergence to the analytical solution.

4.2 Rayleigh-Taylor Instability

The **Rayleigh-Taylor (RT) instability** arises when a denser fluid is accelerated into a lighter fluid, causing perturbations at the interface and the formation of complex vortical structures [66]. This fundamental fluid instability underpins many natural and engineering phenomena. Although the idealized, undisturbed RT instability is rarely observed in practice, its core mechanisms manifest over a broad range of spatial and temporal scales. These mechanisms are influenced by parameters such as viscosity, surface tension, compressibility, external accelerations, and stratification [67].

(a) Absolute error in the location of the interface

(b) Temperature profile convergence analysis

Figure 11: Error analysis for the Stefan problem across various mesh refinements.

Perturbation growth is driven by opposing gradients of pressure and density localized at the interface. The density contrast is quantified by the non-dimensional Atwood number,

$$At = \frac{\rho_H - \rho_L}{\rho_H + \rho_L},$$

where ρ_H and ρ_L denote the densities of the heavier (upper) and lighter (lower) fluids, respectively. Larger Atwood numbers correspond to stronger instability.

The nonlinear evolution of the RT instability governs a wide class of two-phase flows involving fluid penetration or displacement [68]. Simulating this instability accurately is considered a classical benchmark for two-phase flow solvers, requiring detailed resolution of interface dynamics and precise implementation of interphase momentum and surface tension forces [69].

Consider a two-dimensional rectangular domain $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^2$,

$$\Omega = \{(x, y) \in \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R} : x \in [0, L^*), y \in [0, 4L^*)\}$$

occupied by immiscible, viscous, incompressible fluids in subregions Ω_H and Ω_L , satisfying $\Omega = \Omega_H \cup \Omega_L$. The interface location is described by a scalar height function $h(x, t)$:

$$\Omega_i(t) = \{(x, y) \in \mathbb{R}^2 : (-1)^i(y - h(x, t)) > 0, t \geq 0\}, \quad i \in \{H, L\},$$

such that the interface is the curve

$$X(t) = \{(x, y) \in \mathbb{R}^2 : y = h(x, t), t \geq 0\}.$$

Figure 12: Problem setup

With initial interface $X(t_0) = X_0$ and initial velocity field $\bar{\mathbf{v}}(t_0) = \bar{\mathbf{v}}_0$, the governing equations of the Rayleigh-Taylor instability in the one-fluid formulation are shown in Eqn. (4.3). The phases are assumed to be incompressible and the jump conditions at the interface consist of the kinematic constraint of no relative phase velocity and the momentum jump.

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho \bar{\mathbf{v}}) = 0, \quad \text{in } \Omega(t), \quad (4.3a)$$

$$\frac{\partial(\rho \bar{\mathbf{v}})}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho \bar{\mathbf{v}} \otimes \bar{\mathbf{v}}) = -\nabla p + \mu \nabla^2 \bar{\mathbf{v}} + \rho \bar{\mathbf{g}}, \quad \text{in } \Omega(t), \quad (4.3b)$$

$$\nabla \cdot \bar{\mathbf{v}} = 0, \quad \text{in } \Omega(t), \quad (4.3c)$$

$$[[\bar{\mathbf{v}}]] = 0, \quad \text{on } X(t), \quad (4.3d)$$

$$[[\left(\mu (\nabla \bar{\mathbf{v}} + (\nabla \bar{\mathbf{v}})^T) - (p + \rho \bar{\mathbf{g}} \cdot \bar{\mathbf{x}}) \bar{\mathbf{I}} \right) \cdot \bar{\mathbf{n}}]] = \sigma \kappa \bar{\mathbf{n}} + [[\rho]] \bar{\mathbf{g}}, \quad \text{on } X(t), \quad (4.3e)$$

$$\bar{\mathbf{v}}(\bar{\mathbf{x}}, t_0) = \bar{\mathbf{v}}_0, \quad \text{for } t_0 = 0, \quad (4.3f)$$

$$X(t_0) = X_0, \quad \text{for } t_0 = 0, \quad (4.3g)$$

where \bar{n} is the unit normal on the interface, $\bar{\mathbf{I}}$ the identity tensor, and κ the mean curvature of the interface.

To impose a single-mode perturbation, the initial interface is defined as

$$X_0 = 2L_x + A \cos\left(\frac{2\pi x}{L_x}\right),$$

where $A = 0.1L^*$ is the amplitude of the perturbation.

The numerical simulation of the Rayleigh-Taylor instability is performed using STAR-CCM+ over a two-dimensional computational domain. The domain, similar to the problem description, is a rectangle of size $L_x = 1.0$ m in the horizontal direction and $4L_x = 4.0$ m in the vertical direction.

The domain is discretized using a trimmed cell mesher, producing a uniform structured mesh of quadrilateral cells with base size Δh_m . Mesh alignment and local refinements are not applied.

The flow consists of two immiscible, incompressible fluids with constant densities ρ_H and ρ_L and dynamic viscosities μ_H , μ_L . Turbulence is modeled using the Shear Stress Transport (SST) $k-\omega$ model with low-Reynolds number damping for cases where the Reynolds number exceeds the turbulence onset threshold. The multiphase model is employed with a modified High-Resolution Interface Capturing (HRIC) scheme. Surface tension is modeled as a constant coefficient $\sigma = 1.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ N m}^{-1}$, treated semi-implicitly. Gravity acts downward as $\bar{\mathbf{g}} = [0, -1.0] \text{ m s}^{-2}$. The segregated flow solver operates with SIMPLE pressure-velocity coupling. Convective and diffusive fluxes are discretized with second-order upwind schemes, and gradients are computed via a least squares method. The modified HRIC blends the second- and first-order upwind schemes while discretising the Physical parameters and numerical details are chosen to maintain dynamic similarity with the canonical DNS study in [70]. Prior literature suggests that a mesh of 128×512 cells suffices to capture RT instability at $At \approx 0.75$ [71]. The timestep is non-dimensionalized using the Atwood number, and chosen as

$$\Delta t = \frac{2.5 \times 10^{-4}}{\sqrt{At}} \text{ s}$$

in line with analogous studies [72, 70].

Boundary conditions consist of slip walls on the top and bottom boundaries and symmetry (periodic) boundaries on the left and right sides. Initial conditions impose a perturbed interface defined by a cosine wave of amplitude $A = 0.1L_x$ m, with initial velocity set to zero throughout the domain.

Simulation results are monitored by extracting volume fractions and velocity fields along specified planes to analyze interface evolution.

These simulation parameters ensure dynamic similarity with benchmark direct numerical simulations [70], providing a reliable basis for validation and analysis of Rayleigh-Taylor instability development.

Figure 13: Evolution of Rayleigh-Taylor instability for Atwood number $At = 0.5$ at different Reynolds numbers.

Simulation Setup	
Mesh type and size, Δh	Quadrilateral trimmed cell mesh, 4.5×10^{-3} m
Time discretization	Implicit unsteady, first-order Euler
Time step, Δt	3.5×10^{-3} s
Physical Properties	
Amplitude of perturbation, A	0.1 m
Wavelength of perturbation, λ	$L_x = 1.0$ m
Surface tension, σ	1.0×10^{-5} N m ⁻¹
Gravity, \bar{g}	$[0, -1.0]$ m s ⁻²
Numerical Methods	
Multiphase model	VOF with first-order HRIC convection scheme
Flow regime	Turbulent, SST k - ω model
Discretisation scheme	Second-order upwind (flow, volume fraction)
Gradient reconstruction	Least-squares

Table 2: Simulation parameters and physics models for the Rayleigh-Taylor instability study.

Fig. 13 depicts the evolution of the RT instability for Reynolds numbers 300, 1000, and 3000. The initial evolution of the interface is through exponential growth of the infinitesimal disturbance of the interface [73]. The growth follows linear stability theory which transitions into increasing non-linear behaviour as the amplitude grows to orders of 0.1λ [67]. This non-linear evolution is marked by the development of the distinct "bubbles" of lighter fluid rising as the "spikes" of the heavier fluid fall down. The evolving interface experiences increasing vorticity and the increasing velocity shear results in the development of Kelvin-Helmholtz type instabilities [70, 68] leading to the roll-up of the spikes as the amplitude grows to the order of $0.5 - 1\lambda$. For the case of $Re = 3000$, these instabilities are noticeable much earlier all along the interface, leading to a secondary perturbation along the boundary of the domain. Further growth leads to secondary vortices along the spike ends which leads to chaotic mixing and complex flow features. [67].

Effect of Reynolds and Atwood Number

Increasing the Reynolds number has a relatively small effect on the penetration lengths of the spikes and bubbles - with $Re = 300$ showing the least penetration depths. However, it does have a significant effect on the topology of the interface, with increasingly chaotic vortices visible at the spike rollup and the ensuing turbulent mixing. At $Re = 300$, it is seen in Fig. 13, that the flow remains relatively laminar with smooth interfaces, whereas $Re = 3000$ shows significant turbulent mixing and vortical complex structures. High Atwood numbers promote non-linearity and increased turbulent mix-

Figure 14: Evolution of the RT instability with varying Reynolds and Atwood numbers

ing, and affect the initial interface growth. The effect and prominence of the counter-rotating vortices at the tip of the spike decreases and reduces the chaotic flow features at the tips of the secondary vortices. The spike also falls much quicker. This is due to the density-driven acceleration outweighing the viscous effects as is seen in Fig. 17 and in the very high density ratio simulations of the RT instability in [74].

Grid Convergence

In order to evaluate the quality of the mesh, the maximum vertical distance of the spike and bubble tip as measured from the undisturbed initial interface, $y^* = |y_{s,b} - y_0|$, are evaluated for Reynolds numbers, $Re = 300, 3000$, and Atwood number, $At = 0.5$. Locations of the spike and bubble tips are recorded at every time-step and extrapolated in order to compare to the DNS data available from [70].

Fig. 15 shows the comparison the results of the simulations with the DNS location of the bubble and spike tips along with the root mean square defined as

$$err = \sqrt{\sum_{t_0}^{t_f} (y_b - y_{dns})^2}.$$

Figure 15: Grid convergence analysis for Rayleigh-Taylor instability

Fig. 16 compares the RT instabilities for $Re = 1000, 3000$ and $At = 0.5, 0.2$ respectively without the evaluation of the errors.

Although, STAR-CCM+, qualitatively, accurately simulates the RT instability, the calculated RMS and absolute errors in the bubble and spike tip locations show erratic behaviour with decreasing mesh size. For $Re = 300$, a sudden increase in the RMS error at $\Delta h = 0.0025$ is seen. For higher Reynolds numbers, the bubble tip distances are consistently under-predicted for $Re = 1000, 3000$ at later simulation times. For $Re = 3000$, at later simulation times, secondary perturbations develop at the domain edges. These

Figure 16: Comparison with DNS results for different Reynolds numbers and Atwood numbers

secondary perturbations develop into secondary spikes that interfere with the turbulent vortices at the spike tips and the main spike stem. This is, interestingly, not seen for the coarsest mesh size for $Re = 3000$. This could be developing Kelvin-Helmholtz instabilities at the surface that transition into secondary RT instabilities [75]. Although Kelvin-Helmholtz instabilities develop along the interface at higher Reynolds number, this secondary perturbation is first observed for $Re = 10000$ in [70].

This can be ascribed to either the lower order scheme used in the STAR-CCM+ simulations or the choice of turbulence modelling using eddy-viscosity models instead of completely resolving turbulence. For Atwood number that are not close to zero, the Boussinesq hypothesis is also invalid which is an integral assumption in RANS turbulence models. STAR-CCM+, in order to accommodate the spurious currents that may be introduced through the use of eddy-viscosity models, provides models that aid in the damping of momentum and/or turbulence at the interface, however, the addition of these models leads to significant deviations from the DNS results.

4.3 Liquid Infiltration of Evaporation Chamber

The evaporation chamber and the nozzle are modeled together as a two-dimensional domain, as shown in Fig. 18. During the creation of the 2D model, STAR-CCM+ prescribes it an automatic and unchangeable depth of 1m. To maintain kinematic and dynamic similarity with the actual three-dimensional experiment, the duration of discharge is controlled and the mass flow rates are matched by equating the inlet velocities. Approximately 150mL of water is discharged into the chamber during the exper-

Figure 17: Evolution of Rayleigh-Taylor instability for high Atwood numbers $At = 30$, 1000, and 1500.

Figure 18: The meshed domain after the initial adaptive refinement steps for the infiltration problem

iment. The inlet diameter, $d_{\text{in}} = 0.017\text{m}$, is taken as the reference length. Assuming a discharge time $t_{\text{dis}} = 10\text{s}$ and a constant volumetric flow rate, the inflow velocity of water in the experiment can be calculated as

$$\dot{Q} = \frac{Q}{t_{\text{dis}}} = \frac{0.00015}{10} = v \left(\frac{\pi d_{\text{in}}^2}{4} \right),$$

where Q is the total volume discharged. The flow rate is assumed constant over the discharge period. Thus, the inlet velocity depends on the discharge time according to

$$v = \frac{0.00015}{d_{\text{in}} t_{\text{dis}}}.$$

This relation allows the choice of scales to be simple. The diameter of the inlet d_{in} is taken to be the reference length L^* in the simulation. The inflow velocity is thus the reference velocity U^* , and the resulting reference time is given as $t^* = L^*/U^*$. The gravitational acceleration vector is assumed to be $g = 0.4\text{m s}^{-2}$ directed along the negative y -axis.

In the actual 3D experiment, the water height at the end of the injection under steady-state conditions can be estimated, using geometrical data and the volume of discharged water, to be approximately 42 mm. In the simulation, the water injection is terminated at about 2.75 s, after which the water level reaches roughly 42 mm. Subsequently, the simulation continues for an additional 5 s with no inflow velocity imposed.

Section probes located along the mid-section of the evaporation chamber (at heights 25, 35, and 45mm respectively) and at various points along the nozzle measure temperature in a manner replicating the experimental measurement setup. The water-air interface is defined by an isosurface corresponding to a volume fraction of water equal to 0.5. This isosurface indicates the maximum water height along the mid-section probe and is used to record the local velocity component in the y -direction. Water is modelled as an incompressible liquid whereas the air is modelled as an ideal gas. The flow is modelled as unsteady using the volume-of-fluid method and employs a modified HRIC scheme to capture the interface.

The domain is discretised using a trimmed cell mesher using uniform quadrilateral cells refined locally capture interface dynamics accurately. The coarsest mesh size is $d_{in}/2$ and the finest mesh size is chosen to be $d_{in}/32$. This refinement is performed using the Remeshing solver in conjunction with a user defined field function that switches to a finer mesh size based on the local volume fraction. To account for the possibility of heat exchange between the system and the surrounding due to conduction and negligible convection, the walls of the domain are prescribed using a thermal convection boundary. The coefficient of heat transfer is assumed to be $1\text{W m}^{-2}\text{K}^{-1}$ and the thermal resistance is calculated using the chamber dimensions. This resistance is added in parallel to the thermal resistance assumed from the insulating foil around the chamber and nozzle. The simulation assumes a total thermal resistance over the system boundary as $0.098\text{m}^2\text{K W}^{-1}$.

Surface tension is modeled using a constant coefficient $\sigma = 1.0 \times 10^{-5}\text{N m}^{-1}$, treated semi-implicitly. Gravity acts downward as $\bar{g} = [0, -0.4]\text{m s}^{-2}$. The segregated flow solver operates with SIMPLE pressure-velocity coupling. Convective and diffusive fluxes are discretized with second-order upwind schemes, and gradients are computed via a least squares method. The integration in time is performed using the first-order implicit Euler scheme.

Spatial and Temporal Convergence

In order to assess the spatial convergence of the solution, four uniform quadrilateral meshes are used. Using the reference length, L^* , the mesh sizes from coarse to fine are $\Delta h_1 = d_{in}/4$, $\Delta h_2 = d_{in}/8$, $\Delta h_3 = d_{in}/16$, and $\Delta h_4 = d_{in}/32$ respectively. A uniform timestep, $\Delta t = 0.001\text{s}$ is used for all the meshes along with the same initial conditions. Data is recorded at every 0.01 s. The maximum height of the isosurface against the middle section is used to measure the water level. The velocities at various points along the middle section of the chamber are also recorded. Fig. 19 depicts the recorded water level against simulation time and the y -axis component of the velocities measured along the middle section at the simulation stop time, t_f for the above stated mesh sizes. All quantities have been non-dimensionalised using the reference length, velocity, and time scales. The free surface on the coarsest mesh size, h_1 , tends to be

Figure 19: Water level and y -axis velocity component at time, t_f , for various mesh refinements for timestep $\Delta t = 0.001$ s.

have like a vibrating membrane with no significant development of any waves. The fluid bulk does not contain any air pockets as the mesh is too coarse to resolve any fine details at early times. The finer mesh, h_2 , is able to resolve bubbles in the fluid bulk during times of low bubble velocities and when the bubble diameter spans at least four cells. The coarse mesh is, however, able to resolve waves and the oscillatory motion of the isosurface is clearly noticeable. The finest mesh size h_4 is able to resolve merging and breaking apart of the bubbles, droplets escaping the bulk fluid, as well as the flow features developed due to the interaction between the phases at the free surface. The mesh h_3 while also resolving the bubble interactions in the bulk flow and some coarse droplets, is unable to resolve the interface as sharply. However, the increasing void fraction is apparent with decreasing mesh size.

The effects of the choice of timestep is similarly evaluated and is seen in Fig. 20. Using a uniform mesh size Δh_4 , the simulation is run for timesteps 0.0005 s, 0.001 s, and 0.002 s. With shorter timesteps, the duration of the initial peak in water level gets shorter, however no stark difference in flow behaviour is observed as in the case of spatial refinements. Based on the above observations, the mesh size Δh_4 and timestep $\Delta t = 0.001$ s is used as the finest mesh and the standard timestep.

Evolution of the Interface and Flow Field

The evolution of the solution is highly sensitive even with very conservative values for timesteps and mesh size. The development is mostly symmetric but loses symmetry due to the clashing waves produced by impact against the boundaries. This entails mixing where bubbles of air get captured inside the fluid field. Two main churning motions are observed in the fluid flow. A larger circular convection of air is observed in the upper part. This can be due to shear influences of the liquid and the interphase en-

Figure 20: Water level and y-axis velocity component at time, t_f , for various timestep refinements at Δh_4 .

Figure 21: Interface at time, $t = 3.25$ s, with increasing mesh refinement from left to right - Δh_1 , Δh_2 , Δh_3 , and Δh_4 .

ergy exchange. Fig. 22 displays the temperature and pressure recorded by the probes in the nozzle area as would be in the actual experimental setup. The nozzle observes an increasing temperature with increasing water inflow. This temperature cools down equally rapidly due to the energy exchange with the water after inflow has stopped. At the end of the simulation, the recorded temperatures are lower than the temperatures in the water bulk as shown in the surface averages measured along the main body section planes which record a stable temperature of 353 K. The pressure at the end of the infiltration process is recorded to be at ≈ 1.35 bar which is the stipulated pressure at the end of the infiltration process in the actual experiment. Void fractions measuring existence of air pockets in the water also record almost negligible values concluding that the infiltration is not turbulent enough to produce thorough mixing of the water and air into a bubble mixture as the system gets enough time to somewhat stabilise. The flow field is visualised using line integral convolutions of the velocity field. Along with this temperature behaviour during infiltration times is depicted in Fig. 23

Figure 22: Pressure, temperature, and void fraction measurements using the surface average values at plane sections in the computational domain.

4.4 Summary

Numerical studies of the described benchmarks show convergent Stefan-front tracking and qualitatively correct Rayleigh-Taylor instability behaviour, with noted discrepancies at higher Reynolds numbers attributable to model order and RANS assumptions. The infiltration simulations provide resolved interface dynamics and stable thermohydraulic end-states (water level, temperature field, and chamber pressure) that match the experimental envelope and serve as credible initial conditions for subsequent flash-evaporation modeling.

Figure 23: Flow field visualisations using line integral convolutions and the behaviour of temperature during the infiltration process

5 Conclusion

In this last chapter, we provide a brief summary of major topics covered in the thesis and assess the impending future work.

5.1 Summary

In this thesis we,

- studied the physical phenomenon of flash evaporation. We reviewed the contradictory effects of low-pressure and low-gravity environments to liquid-gas phase change phenomena. We review the existing flash evaporation models and their capabilities, limits, and applicabilities to different flow scenarios. Based on experimental observations and review of literature, we identified the governing factors in an accurate modelling of flash evaporation.
- revisited the multiphase flow models for two-phase liquid-gas systems and detailed the context of jump conditions in the models. We also discuss turbulence and describe the numerical implementation of these models in STAR-CCM+.
- assessed the complex maze of closure relations for the interphase interactions in the two-fluid model and arrived at a set of generally applicable closures based on physical principles instead of empirical coefficients.
- modelled the 1D Stefan problem and the 2D Rayleigh-Taylor instability. This was done to assess the treatment of a moving interface in the context of a fixed grid method like the finite-volume method. The Stefan problem also serves as a benchmark to test for the accurate modelling of the phase change phenomenon. The Rayleigh-Taylor instability is a fundamental phenomenon in two-phase flows with a significant density difference. The limitations of our assumptions in context of high Reynolds numbers and turbulence are discussed in this context.
- described the mathematical formulation of the infiltration of water in a low-pressure chamber which was subsequently modelled using the Volume-of-Fluid method. We implemented adaptive mesh refinement based on user-defined field functions in order to refine the mesh locally during flow evolution. We finally analysed the flow evolution and determined the initial conditions expected in the flash evaporation subproblem.

5.2 Outlook

While this thesis investigated the factors affecting a modelling framework for flash evaporation, the problem remains unmodelled and forms the immediate next steps.

- An assessment of the effects of RANS turbulence models is required for flash evaporation applications. Investigations combining a hybrid RANS-LES approaches could be suitable possibilities.
- Building on the validated treatment of two-phase flows using the VOF method, investigations could be performed identifying the possibility of modelling phase change using phase specific source terms in STAR-CCM+. Equilibrium conditions can be enforced by disregarding the energy equation solver and implementing an additional scalar equation to treat temperature.
- An ideal flash evaporation model would account for the homogeneous and heterogeneous nucleation rates along with phase transfer at the interface governed by the kinetic theory. To this end, a scalar equation solving for the conservation of the number of bubbles in the system can be solved. This would enable consistent interfacial area concentration and closure feedback for heat, mass, and momentum exchange.

5.2.1 A Theoretical Stipulation

To model flashing under rapid depressurisation with thermal and velocity non-equilibrium, we propose an Eulerian Multiphase (two-fluid) formulation with Large-Scale Interface capabilities, coupled to interfacial area concentration (IAC) transport, a bubble population balance for number density and nucleation, and a kinetic interfacial mass-flux closure of Schrage type.

Governing phasic balances and sources. For each phase $i \in \{l, v\}$, solve the volume-averaged mass, momentum, and energy balances as in the two-fluid model with a mass source in the governing equations to the the kinetic mass transfer using the Schrage equation.

Interfacial area concentration transport. Evolve the IAC field a_{lv} to reflect transient nucleation, growth, coalescence/breakage, and phase change:

$$\frac{\partial a_{lv}}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (a_{lv} \mathbf{u}_{mix}) = S_{nuc} + S_{grw} - S_{coal} - S_{brk} + S_{pc},$$

where S_{nuc} adds area from newly nucleated bubbles, S_{grw} accounts for radius change \dot{R} , S_{coal} and S_{brk} model topology changes, and S_{pc} captures interfacial recession/advance due to phase change at large interfaces (LSI regime). In dispersed-bubble cells, relate a_{lv} to the bubble size distribution $n(d)$ by

$$a_{lv} = \int_0^{\infty} \pi d^2 n(d) dd \quad (\text{spherical bubbles}).$$

Population balance for bubble number density. Solve a number-density transport for diameter d (or radius R) with growth velocity $G = \dot{d}$, coalescence/breakage kernels, and nucleation sources:

$$\frac{\partial n}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (n \mathbf{u}_v) + \frac{\partial}{\partial d}(G n) = B_{nuc}(d) + B_{coal}(d) + B_{brk}(d) - D_{coal}(d) - D_{brk}(d).$$

Bubble growth law and thermal coupling. Use a composite growth rate that superposes inertial- and thermal-limits, consistent with diffusion-controlled Stefan scaling at later times:

$$\dot{R} = \sqrt{\frac{2(p_{sat}(T_l^{int}) - p_l)}{3\rho_l}} + \frac{\rho_l c_{p,l} |T_l^{int} - T_{sat}(p_l)|}{\rho_v h_{lv}} \sqrt{\frac{3\alpha_l}{\pi t}},$$

and couple to \dot{m} by enforcing local interfacial energy balance and consistent choices of T_l^{int} , T_{int} , and heat-transfer coefficients for q_i^{int} .

Algorithmic outline for the flashing stage.

1. Initialise from the infiltration end-state: fields $(\alpha_i, \mathbf{v}_i, T_i, p)$, set vacuum/outflow boundary and depressurisation profile.
2. Enable EMP with multiregime blending and activate PBE+IAC in dispersed regions; seed initial $n(d)$ from known particulate load or a uniform low background consistent with silicate content.
3. Compute nucleation source B_{nuc} using CNT with heterogeneous correction where walls/impurities dominate; map to $n(d)$ and update a_{lv} .
4. Advance \dot{R} and $G = \dot{d}$ with thermal coupling; update a_{lv} and $n(d)$ including coalescence/breakage.
5. Evaluate kinetic \dot{m} (Schrage) and apply $\Gamma_i = a_{lv}\dot{m}, \dot{Q}$, and interfacial momentum sources in phasic balances; iterate to convergence per time-step.
6. Remesh/refine adaptively near rapid void-fraction transients and LSI interfaces; limit interface Courant number and apply interface-turbulence damping if needed.

This plan provides a theoretically working NHNEM pathway with physics-based interfacial exchanges, retaining slip and non-equilibrium, while remaining compatible with STAR-CCM+ EMP/LSI numerics.

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